

Dynamical malaria modelling as a tool for bold policy-making

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To the Editor - The malaria community have been called upon to be bold¹. Pedro Alonso's Comment asked the malaria community to adapt established interventions to new areas, to tailor preventive strategies to local contexts, and to strive to reach the hard-to-reach¹. We would like to highlight the pivotal role that dynamical modelling can and does play in making these necessary policy shifts

Malaria is complex. Describing its dynamics requires an understanding of the parasite, the various mosquito vectors, the human hosts' level of immunity and human behaviour, as well as the policy landscape and environment in which all three interact. Dynamical modelling suites for malaria, such as the Swiss Tropical and Public Health Institute's OpenMalaria, provide platforms where all these factors can be taken into account simultaneously^{2,3}. After adequately capturing the current state of malaria in a given setting, we use the calibrated model as a tool to explore the potential impact of deploying additional interventions. Dynamical modelling has many limitations, is inherently replete with uncertainty, and can only ever be as trustworthy as the data upon which it rests. But even given these caveats, with its evidence-based, explicit and interrogable assumptions, modelling provides a framework for comparing possible approaches.

Modelling has a formalised place within the WHO's High Burden to High Impact process, which aims to accelerate reduction of malaria risk in the eleven highest burden countries⁴. The watchwords of High Burden to High Impact are "political engagement" and "using data for action", with dynamical modelling playing a key role in the latter. In this process, policy-makers in each country create national malaria control plans, tailoring the interventions to the epidemiological context in each geographical area. The potential impact of each of these sub-nationally tailored plans are then modeled, and the results used to help finalise strategies and prioritise resources during funding requests to national and international donors.

Expanding seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) into untested areas offers another example of modelling's role in policy change. SMC is a highly effective malaria intervention suitable for areas with seasonal malaria transmission; preventively treating children monthly for the duration of the malarial season. In the past eight or so years, SMC has been widely deployed across the Sahel, where it likely averts several million cases annually⁵. But, mainly due to the assumption that drug resistance would render the intervention ineffective, it has never been implemented outside the Sahel, despite other areas of Africa also seeing malaria cases concentrated during well-defined rainy seasons. The Karamoja region of Uganda is such a place, with most rain falling within a five-month period, starting in May.

Malaria prevalence in Karamoja has long been substantially higher than in other regions of Uganda, and its population is largely nomadic, hampering bed net usage. In short, it seems like a region ripe for SMC.

Ugandan policy-makers envisioned deploying SMC in Karamoja as a way to finally make a dent in the region's persistently high malaria burden. As a first step, they reached out to dynamical modelers. Together, we modelled the deployment plan of monthly rounds of SMC from May to September, as well as a series of scenarios in which we varied each of our model assumptions in turn. Baseline levels of malaria incidence shape the impact of any malaria intervention, and incidence can vary wildly within even a small area. For these reasons, we projected our SMC deployment scenarios across a range of incidence levels, rather than using the regional-level estimate.

From a modeler's perspective, there were several key findings of the exercise. Firstly, effect size (measured as percentage reduction in incidence compared to the scenario with no SMC deployment) is lowest when baseline incidence is lowest; secondly, any intended or unintended deviations to the deployment plan likely cause less perturbation to the effect size when baseline incidence is higher; and thirdly, the SMC component being less efficacious than in the Sahel, and coverage decaying substantially with each monthly round would do most to drag down the expected effect size at all incidence levels.

From an implementor's perspective, the modelling exercise acted mainly as powerful advocacy for the plan; offering proof of the concept that SMC could work in this uncharted territory. Secondly, it galvanised efforts to achieving high coverage throughout the SMC cycles. The preliminary results of an ongoing implementation trial in two of Karamoja's nine districts look very promising and hopefully SMC can soon be rolled out across the region.

Boldness is demanded if we are to solve the intractable problem of malaria. But bold visions require evidence before they can be turned into bold actions at the population and community level - dynamical modelling is here for it.

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Author contributions

All authors were involved in the conceptualisation of this correspondence. BNO, MW and EP contributed to the dynamical modelling methodology, analysis and validation. BNO prepared the first draft. All authors were involved in review and editing.

Competing interests

All authors declare having no competing interests

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